

THE CONCEPT OF THE TERM AND ITS PLACE IN MEDICINE

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ABSTRACT

The article covers general information about terminology and their importance in linguistics. Terminology the problem that arise in the translation of medical terms and how to find solutions to them were discussed.

Key words: *terminology, linguistics, terms, medicine, dentistry, pharmaceuticals, phonetic, grammatical, lexical.*

Nowadays, there are more attention to work with terms in linguistics than in the past. And many scientists are doing research in this field. Terms are commonly used to express clearly scientific concepts in one meaning. In Uzbek linguistics, a lot of work has been done on the study of terms. There are several types of scientific books, pamphlets, dictionaries, scientific articles and scientific-popular articles in terms of terminology. The publication of more than 200 dictionaries is a great achievement of linguistics. Update the law on the state language status of the Uzbek language, “Adoption of the Uzbek alphabet based on the Latin script”, further strengthening of the field of terminology caused it to rise to a higher level. The “term” means “border” in Latin language. The change of terms’ structure and meaning is an essential event for not only history of language but also history of people.

The main purpose of Uzbek terminology is to clarify the history of the Uzbek language and some of its unclear issues. The study of terms may contribute to indicate

the phonetic, lexical. Grammatical, stylistic and synonymic standards of the language, as well as orthography and for generalizing orthoepy. Because of the limitation of the term. In other words the terms express one meaning it keep its meaning in a special context. It does not have emotional and expressive features. The meaning of the term does not change with the help of tone. So, the term is a set of words related to a certain field. For this reason, words have a specific meaning in a certain field are called terms O.P.Frolova gives the following definition to “terminology”: It is known that a system of terms of a science corresponds to a system of concept and a specific system of terms depends on any system of concepts. With the development of science, the system of terns also develops” .

The formation of Uzbek terminology can be divided into three stages. These are the terminology of the ancient Turkish language (VII-X), the terminology of the old Turkish language(XI-XIV), the terminology of the old Uzbek literary language (XV-XX). In addition to the period of independence the terminology of the Uzbek language was formed at that time. Day by day, the field of Uzbek terminology was developed. Needless to say, the field of terminology has a special place and position in the construction of the modern Uzbek literary language. The role of terminology in the vocabulary is significantly large and contributes to the increase of vocabulary. The field of terminology is one of the current directions of modern linguistic research. Terminology is a large part of the vocabulary of all languages. Therefore, the science of terminology continues to develop rapidly, because terminology also allows the creation of new words in the language.

Since there are a great number of terms in Uzbek language, they have to be learnt by dividing groups according to theme. As Uzbek terminologists such as S.Ibrohimov, S.Akobirov, Olim Usmon, R.Doniyorov, X.Shamsiddinov, M.Madvaliyev mentioned, this kind of learning helps to show general richness of terms and learn by dividing into various fields.

At first, terms are divided into two groups:

1. The term which have general features
2. The term which have specific features

General terms are understandable in all directions of certain terminology system. For example some terms in medicine such as operation, aspirin, injection, laboratory can be used in all fields of medicine. Specific terms are used in only one certain branch. For instance, pathology, anaphylactic shock inhalation vaccination and other terms like these can only be used few particular areas.

Nowadays, development of medicine branches such as dentistry, pharmaceuticals can lead to increase of Uzbek terminological vocabulary. Currently terms and terminological systems related to almost all fields of science and medicine have appeared in Uzbek language. Although terms are words that openly express concepts related to a certain field but the use of those words is known and understandable only to people in this field. We can consider this on the example of dental and pharmaceutical terms of medicine. When translating terms into Uzbek, it is important to study them carefully.

To this day, about term and terminology in our country and although a lot of research has been done in this field, this is still not the case the topic has not lost its interest in linguistics. There is a term of the world and a terminologist, it is necessary to reveal the full and detailed linguistic structure. There is a need to carry out research, of course. The term is a great lesson in the vocabulary of the national language and many researchers have given their opinion about the composition of the layer have reached.

In our opinion, term its linguistic nature, the lexical system of the literary language is an inventive term, rather than a scientific term of another category, clear and concise expression of technical and other technical concepts and It is rich in information. Regarding terminology in the next year, the researcher is the leader in local and ethnic linguistics taking the place. To this, the science and technology of the present day is accelerated brewing, striving for innovation, integration, increasing the

size of the scientific and technical database day by day as a result, the terminological lesson is about to expand. To the existence of a fully systematic pharmaceutical terminologist arrival and the linguistic level of the lexicon of this field

To solve the problem is to touch the long tapestry of the innocent past is worn. Etymological origin of the word some pharmaceutical terms in the Uzbek language There are a few of the doctors who lived and worked in the East countries

Abu Al Ibn Sino was a pioneer for his generation, and today he is a scientific leader in the world It has been a long time for research and development, a world-renowned thinker who has been revered throughout the world, the place of the scholar known as Avicenna in the West world care Abu Ali ibn Sino, with his rich scholar. UNECKO organization is written by Ibn Sino "Medical law" is about to celebrate the thousandth anniversary of Arab. A national gold medal was awarded to him for his acceptance of the desicion and his interpretation and the success of the world cup of medicine.

REFERENCES:

1. *Akobirov S.F, Til va terminologiya, T., O'zbekiston. 1968y. 22-23 betlar*
2. *Oktamovna, S. Z., & Nasriyevich, G.N (2021) Terminology as a structural element of the language. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 10(9), 724-731.*
3. *Abdurashitovna, A.S. (2020) The influence of motivation in the foreign language learning process. Наука и образование сегодня, (6-2(53)), 37-38.*
4. *Акобиров С. Тил ва терминология. – Тошкент, 1968*
5. <https://www.uobabylon.edu.iq/eprints/publication>
6. *Pekler M.A 1967: 15, Rachstein A.D.1980: 116*
7. *Ирискулов М. Тилишуносликка кириш. – Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 1992.*
8. *Суперанская А.В. Общая терминология. Терминологическая деятельность. - М.: УРСС, 1993. - 288с.*